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A STUDY IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF E.R.P. THROUGH ETHICAL SYSTEMS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The ERP was a significant step in an ongoing evolution of computer tools that began in the late 1960's. It evolved out of Material Resource Planning (MRP). Each chronological step is built on the fundamentals and principles developed within the earlier one. Information Technology has had a major impact on these trends. These are the important and new concepts have been in developing stage.

Paper is the amalgam of two separate studies conducted in Pune and in Jaipur under the same Supervisor and is assimilated for publication herein.

This paper(i) highlights some of the issues on which organization can decide to develop an expert system for decision making in implementation of ERP and comments on the reasons for its failure based on the author's investigative research..(ii) In doing so, the author raises certain vital issues that decision makers have to contend with and face up to.

Key Words: Material Resource Planning, ERP, Ethical Systems Development.

1. INTRODUCTION: The business environment has become increasingly complex and the marketplace has changed from local to global leading to fierce competition. Management is under tremendous pressure to take cost control initiatives, analyze costs/revenues on a product or customer basis, improving logistics and providing better customer support services. ERP is the latest high-end business solution aims to equip the management with the right information to take timely decisions. This will bring about logical acceptance, consistency and reliability. The expert system has to deal with a bipolar reality in which technology occupies one pole and people the other. The system, it is argued, must be fair to both people and technology.

The direction and pace of change is non-Newtonian and non-linear. Change is like a fluid which it at once a solid, a liquid and a gas. Structures and functions are concurrently collapsing and managers are expected to be multi-functional and multi-tasking. The organization structure that emanates is the Matrix Structure where there is a great deal of fuzziness and decisions are expected to be made under conditions of relative uncertainty. Hence, only a strong system and process chain that can absorb and react to change in the environment can guarantee some element of scientific objectivity in decision-making. This is what the ERP is expected to deliver. In short, the system is expected to enable the organization to generate and collect data, analyze the same along pre-determined parameters and deliver decisions in accordance with certain "rules". These rules can be *substantive* in that they answer the question *why* or they can be *procedural* in that they answer the question *how*.

Given the above, some of the major functions of ERP for the business systems are as follows:

- It helps in integrating the data emerging out from functional areas such as manufacturing, supply chain management, human resources, CRM and data warehouses etc. this simplified access to information empower employees and managers while boosting motivation, productivity, and efficiency.
- It ensures compliance and predictability of business performance, enabling the managers to gain a deeper financial insight across the enterprise and tighten control of finances.
- It provides the complete integration of systems not only across the departments in a company but also across the companies under the same management.
- It helps in optimizing the human resources which leads to better organization, maximize the potential of workforce, while supporting innovation, growth and flexibility.
- ERP allows automatic introduction of latest technologies like Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT), Electronic data Interchange (EDI), Internet, Intranet, video conferencing, E-commerce etc.
- It optimizes both centralized and decentralized for managing real estate, enterprise assets, project portfolios, corporate travel, Environment, Health and safety (EH&S), quality and global trade services.
- It supports the entire life cycle of performance management, delivering real-time, personalized measurements and metrics to improve business insight and decision making.

The ERP software systems have been evolving gradually, and ERP as an expert system for management application has been around since 1960's. Until 1972, ERP was just a concept and as such very much in the *substantive realm*. With competition raising the bar for performance, an expert system had to be (a) cost effective (b) result oriented and (c) able to assist management to take decisions. This concept was to

integrate all departments and functions, increase revenues, and strengthen the business. ERP systems became synonymous with competitive advantage, particularly through the 1990's.

Being and improvement from MRP, the ERP systems replaced isolated information with a single, packaged software solution that integrates all traditional enterprise management functions like Finance, Accounting, Manufacturing, Human Resource Management and Logistics. The ERP systems brought a common information database, which helped business functions of the organization to shift their thinking to an organization or enterprise-focus rather than a departmental one. So doing it moved on to the *procedural realm*.

Implementation of ERP is not an easy task. ERP system should have support and involvement from all the people in the organization. If the system is implemented without the support of all these people then the chances of failure of implementation are more. This is a major change from the isolated systems landscape. It becomes the joint responsibility of the CEO and the HR Head to sell the idea of ERP in such a way that people "own" the idea and are therefore "a party to its implementation success." Unfortunately this is not always the case. The greatest threats to any expert system are three folds: (a) lack of understanding of what they can deliver, (b) expecting miracles and (c) unwillingness to change. In the light of these three (possible) constraints, is it ethical on the part of people as well as technology to be used in introducing an expert system?

ERP systems have to be tailor made to suit organizations' needs and the personnel involved must feel that the system "belongs" to them and that "bonding" between technology and human beings is crucial. Therefore, the role of the *developer* is very important from the organization's point of view. Only when the company puts all its trust in the developer and the organization truly believes that progress and competitive edge will be achieved with the help of development team members, the business goals become more reachable. Depending on the expertise of the developer ERP implementation will become smooth functioning activities to the people of the organization.

However, the *developer* is basically a technology driven person and if he is expected to double up as (i) professional advisor, (ii) change agent and (iii) a qualified resource that has all the answers, he/she invariably fails to perform. This misunderstanding of the role of the developer arises, according to the author, mainly when HR support is not forthcoming, the CEO does not give time for the system to deliver and the mediocrity in the organization is resistant to change.

2. OBJECTIVES OF AN ERP SYSTEM:

Based on our separate studies, we opine that the key objectives of a typical ERP system in an organization are: (a) to provide support for all variations of business practices, (b) to enable implementation of those practices with a view towards enhancing productivity, and (c) to empower the customer to modify the implemented business processes to suit the organizational needs. In light of the above, it is obvious that one of the main objectives of an ERP system is to provide *vital information* so that *appropriate and timely action* can be taken based upon it. ERP systems give the means by which any organization can make improvements in the areas of quality, production planning and control, time to market, customer service and performance. Therefore, ERP is an instrument of business sustainability as well as developmental growth.

Clear understanding these aspects allow the organization to adapt quickly to changing demands and customer needs, which ultimately leads to higher profits and larger market share plus enhanced customer satisfaction. ERP systems thus provide modern management with a vital tool for decision making in these times of cutthroat competition where the consequences of a wrong decision are multiplied many times over and a right decision just about suffices to keep a wafer-thin lead against the competition. Hence, it would be in order to say the ERP (enterprise resource planning) and CRM (customer relationship management) are intrinsically connected with each other.

According to scholars on organization excellence, Value is seen as a *subjective connotation* when we say, “these are our core beliefs”. Manager or organizations that follow this connotation in daily life are said to be *value based*. Value is also seen as an *objective connotation* when we say, “this is the value added by the person, the process or the product”. Managers or organizations that follow this connotation in daily life are said to be *value driven*. However, if managers or organizations in daily life are both *value based* and *value driven* then they are said to be *value centered*. ERP, this paper holds, ideally promotes value-centered behavior.

In order to understand the attraction of ERP systems, we first need to understand the problems they are designed to solve i.e. to consolidate and obtain synergies within the fragmentation of information in large business organizations. Every big company collects, generates, and stores vast quantities of data. In most companies, data is not kept in a single repository. The managers in charge of a single repository may have goals that are different from the manager of another repository e.g. *cost cutting* vs. *production increasing*. An ERP system subsumes all these legacy systems under a common umbrella so that conflicting goals are reduced considerably and convergence takes place in a meaningful manner.

Usually, the information is spread across dozens or even hundreds of separate computer systems, each housed in an individual function, business unit, region, factory, or office. Each of these so-called legacy systems may provide invaluable support for a particular business activity. But in combination, they represent one of the heaviest drags on business productivity and performance now in existence. Maintaining many different computer systems leads to enormous costs for storing and rationalising redundant data, for re-keying and reformatting data from one system in use into another, for updating and debugging obsolete software code, for programming communication links between systems to automate the transfer of data.

However, even more important than the direct costs are the indirect costs. If a company’s sales and ordering systems cannot talk with its production-scheduling systems, then its manufacturing productivity and customer responsiveness suffer. If its sales and marketing systems are incompatible with its financial-papering systems, then management is left to make important decisions by instinct rather than according to a detailed understanding of product and customer profitability. This is exacerbated by inherent goal conflict between sub-systems and different legacy managers.

Management after all, is the science of decision-making and the art of decision-executing. ERP then becomes an invaluable management instrument. Moreover it must be remembered that a fair degree of empowerment and accountability are called for. As has been argued by Sadri and Jayashree (2009) “empowerment without accountability produces tyrants just as accountability without empowerment creates slaves”. An ERP package should create neither tyrants nor slaves but efficient and effective work processes. Only then can it be called “ethical”.

3. DECISION MAKING IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ERP: The question is then posed: does the organization require an ERP package and is this worth the cost? That means a thorough diagnosis must precede the decision to implement ERP. Many times decisions are taken to implement ERP just because the Manager or Consultant would like that fact to appear in his/her Bio-Data. This is unfortunate but true. Usually when the decision for an implementation is under consideration, the organization often establishes a steering committee, which guides the organization through the entire implementation. This steering committee is responsible for firstly seeing if ERP is needed and secondly whether the time-cost factors are manageable. If it fails in ensuring any of these, questions regarding the ethicality of its decision are automatically raised.

This study focused first on the process involved in the decision making for the ERP Implementation. What contributes to decision-making must be scientifically defensible, logically tenable and realistically implementable. If not, it will remain wishful thinking. It was found that the following three criteria were paramount in the consideration of the steering committees in the ten organizations that were pilot-

studied by this author between 2006 and 2008. (i) Data Volume of the organization. (ii) Business and Operational complexity. (iii) Reporting Complexity.

There has been substantial published work that affirms the fact that the need of the hour is ethical leadership. In the implementation of ERP too ethical leadership is called for so that a win-win situation emerges both for the people and for technology.

The author's found that there were several reasons for increase in the number of ERP implementation sites in the post 1991 era. Right from deciding of whether to go for an ERP up until the post implementation support and enhancements at many sites, the decisions were very much *consultant specific*. Mostly these consultants were experts from outside the ongoing organizational system and so the *level of personal accountability* was debatable. Also, there was no way in which an organization could know if the consultant had any personal ties with the ERP provider giving rise to *professional bias*. Hence, the author's opines that an internal expert must be in the steering committee and he/she must be sufficiently knowledgeable, senior and ethical to be override the consultant (if need be) and thus enable an objective decision.

Coming to post implementation scenario once again an *expert committee* (preferably but not necessarily) separate from the earlier *steering committee* should evaluate the ERP package and once again, care should be taken to address issues concerning (a) *level of personal accountability* and (b) *professional bias*. The consultant must be a member of this committee as well so that there is absolute transparency in decision-making. Once again an internal resource must be a member of the expert committee and he/she must be sufficiently knowledgeable, senior and ethical to be override the consultant (if need be) and thus enable an objective post implementation analysis. This is unfortunately not done, and the amount of fuzziness remains. As long as this fuzziness remains, ethical clarity will continue to evade us.

The author's also found that many consultants were not thoroughly honest with their clients by recommending change *without* bothering to diagnose the environment. Equally true was the fact that academicians spoke of HRIS without an adequate computer literacy. Only after the consultant is convinced that he/she is ethical, has conducted a proper diagnosis and found that an ERP package is needed for the company, he/she should go ahead and recommend it. Assuming that the consultant is ethical he/she will candidly and plainly lay the cards on the table face upwards. Organizations also have a right to know the key benefits of an ERP System before implementing the package. These must be specific and, if possible, quantified. Unless these (expected) benefits are stated clearly in terms of quantity, quality, cost and time they would remain in the realms of wishful thinking.

Now let us address the question of clarity. Many large organizations have several (strategic business units) SBUs and production sites. There is no reason for all SBUs and geologically dispersed sites to be either functionally or structurally similar, although that helps. For an organization, that has embarked on ERP implementation at different sites or for several business units, which is having manufacturing plants at different locations, the post implementation scenario can be different depending upon the ability of the corresponding location's manager and the local environment. Because of the mutable nature of reality and changed environments, many of the companies studied, needed to a spend lot of resources in terms of money and labor. This was especially so if the need arose for integrating all locations in the ERP solution after individual implementation. The rules of scientific method that encourage us to avoid these three pitfalls must be taken seriously:

- (i) *The Fallacy of Composition*: This arises when we assume that what is true of a part is equally true of the whole.
- (ii) *The Fallacy of Accident*: This arises when we assume that what is true of the whole is equally true for each part.

- (iii) *Post hoc sed non-proctor hoc.* This means that an occurrence *after* an event is not seen to be *because of* that event.

Thus, we require to gather information from multiple consultants who have worked on multiple projects, the tool will have multi consultants, multi implementations knowledge. Moreover, when we gather this information the rules of scientific method must be followed. Whereas it is good to have many internal consultants (managers involved) in the evaluation committee, the rule to follow is that members must *have a divergent specialized skills but convergent organizational aims.*

To take a decision for effective implementation of ERP we require to study the existing system with reference to various operations, procedures, organization structure and different Govt. regulations and policies. Secondly to develop a culture for the implementation of ERP in such a organization. This mainly comprises of knowledge engineering, which is to find out experts and experienced senior officials and end users of the organizations.

Based on the author's pilot study of ten organizations, given below are some of the major benefits that may accrue from implementing ERP solutions:

In terms of Organizational Effectiveness: Effectiveness is nothing but the degree to which an objective is realized. For this, the objective must ideally be expressed in terms of quantity, quality, cost and time dimensions using the well-known SMART principle.

In the case of Corporate Business, this was found to be actualized in the following manner.

- ◆ Improved customer service
- ◆ Faster cycle time to market
- ◆ Improved access to integrated information for more effective decisions (costs, profitability, etc.)
- ◆ Ensures a smoother flow of information at all levels and between all parts of the organization
- ◆ Commonality of global information
- ◆ Replacement of legacy systems that are expensive to maintain and support
- ◆ Workflow integrates business processes
- ◆ Support for post-merger integration
- ◆ Responsiveness to regulatory changes
- ◆ Catalyst/enabler of (cross-functional) organizational renewal
- ◆ Added business functionality
- ◆ Brings together who work on shared tasks within the same enterprise or in their dealings with suppliers and customers

In the case of Information Technology these benefits were found to have been realized in terms of:

- ◆ Flexibility of systems
- ◆ Responsiveness to change
- ◆ Strategic posturing of IT for the future
- ◆ Solution to the Year 2000 problems and the “Euro”

In terms of the Organizational Efficiency: Efficiency is nothing else but the ratio of output to input expressed in percentage terms. For the Business Organization it was actualized in terms of. The following:

- ◆ Reduced costs of business operations
- ◆ Reduced inventories
- ◆ Standardization of business processes across unit, across functions
- ◆ Reduced cost of business information management (e.g., clerical cost of transaction inputs, cost of data reconciliation)

In the case of Information Technology these benefits were realized in terms of:

- ◆ Lower maintenance costs
- ◆ Lower operating costs

Having dealt with the need for decision making and the safeguards needed to ensure scientific objectivity, this paper goes on to enumerate the various tasks that are involved in decision making using ERP a strategic management instrument. This instrument is ideally directed towards managing change.

The steering committee will seriously blunder its way through change unless it understands the organizational climate and its various manifestations and dimensions. By climate this paper means those aspects of the work environment in an organization which are perceived by those employed in the organization and which help them to conform their behavior to expected (or perceived) norms. Research indicates that organizational climate has 12 dimensions which are enumerated briefly below, and which the CEO must take a serious note of.

Vision and Mission: If a person does not know where he is going he cannot get lost. So too an organisation must have a clear vision and a clear mission which are both articulated and known to all. They must be crisp and stimulating personas to action rather than a mere statement of purpose.

Objective and Goal: The former is an open ended attribute which gives the direction of change whereas the latter is a close ended attribute which gives the magnitude of the change. The former is qualitative whereas the latter is essentially quantitative.

Structure: The rules and constraints placed upon the actors must be such that creativity and innovation are made possible. Rules are meant for the benefit of man and not the vice versa. This does not mean that rules will be made and unmade with impunity.

Responsibility: Trust begets trust and accountability without authority leads to neo-feudalistic management behaviour. Here it must be stressed that most management's that administer by exception do so at their own peril.

Risk: He who works will err. Hence punishment for errors made, will only create a risk avoidance syndrome that can do nobody any good. Hence, managements should be induced to take calculated risks within the Bounds of law and ethical propriety.

Reward: Recognition for good work done must be quick and public. The adage that subordinate should be praised in public but rebuked only in private is something which is easily lost sight of in the heat of the moment.

Standards. Emphasis must always be on excellence and goals once realised must be realistically upgraded. Standards cannot be compromised whether they be in the field of production, quality or human behaviour.

Clarity of role: This is so important that merit rating and performance appraisal exercises fall flat on their face without it. Yet, many organisations go through with the annual exercise without bothering to clarify roles first. Such actions are not defensible either in the name *managerial prerogatives* or *situational constraints*: two often used excuses.

Warmth and Support: Goodwill is a prized commodity and when that is lost, no matter how efficient a manager is, success will always elude him. There is the case of a super-efficient secretary to a CEO who has alienated every manager with the result that nobody wishes even to greet her in the morning unless they want to speak to the CEO. The is the other case of a CEO who, in the midst of a strike, went out and spoke to the union leaders over a cup of tea at the factory gate. Both examples show the polarities of behaviour which exist in industrial organisations.

Conflict: This is a very misunderstood term. Confrontation, which results from a clash of ego should be avoided at all costs but conflict which arises out of a clash of opinion should be encouraged and channelled constructively in the organisation interest.

Leadership: Whenever a clique dominates the decision making function, objectivity is lost and progress cannot be achieved. Fresh leadership is discouraged and mediocrity thrives since they are comfortable in saying yes sir without the slightest twinge of conscience.

Technological superiority: Managements, which are comfortable in doing the same old things in the same old way often, find that they have been living in cloud cuckoo-land and the rest of the market forces have passed them by.

A word of caution needs to be inserted here. As Sadri and Jayashree (2009) argue, Climate Surveys need to be conducted expeditiously and accurately such that actions emanating there from are evident. Moreover, regular Action Taken Reports must follow up a survey if it is not to be treated lightly.

4. TASKS INVOLVED IN THE DECISION MAKING: For implementation of ERP following tasks we further opine that are required to be studied in greater detail:

1. **Creating a Knowledge Base:** This is the most difficult step in decision making. For this we require to focus on meetings with managers who are actually involved in the implementation of ERP systems, meeting with ERP vendors and consultants, preparation of proper data samples, preparation of questioner, personal interviews etc .

2. **Dealing with imprecise incorrect and uncertain data:** When data is collected there are chances that you may get incorrect data, imprecise data or in some cases part of the data could be missing. In such cases we have to consider reasoning techniques and certainly factors to arrive at the missing data.
3. **Implementation of the expert system:** This process starts with the generation of rules. After rules generation, designing the rules base using a backend like MS Access and any front end tool can be used for coding

The author's opine that while we develop an Expert System we have to plan for each task as a milestone in the development of Expert System. A milestone does not present anything else but the distance left to be covered to reach the goal. In implementing the ERP package the author further opines that the Sadri and Jayashree (1997) (2003) **5-D Methodology** should be used.

The **first D** stands for **Definition**. There must be absolute clarity of vision, mission, role and goal at every level. This clarity leads to understandable limits and assumptions made while also explaining the *substantive realm* that deals with the *why* and *what* of ERP.

The **second D** stands for **Diagnosis**. There must a rigorous and scientific *need analysis* and study of *cost-price-time constraints* conducted before the ERP package is purchased. For the CEO and the HR Head this will be a valuable tool to "sell the idea" of ERP to the stakeholders and covers the *procedural realm* adequately. Therein the process clarifies the *why* of ERP.

The **third D** stands for **Design**: To avoid putting a *square peg in a round hole*, the ERP package must be tailor made for the organization so that the needs thrown up by diagnosis are suitably addressed. The IT expert involved in this process must be aware that there can be no common package for all organizations or a common rule for systems. Particularized codification for the expert system in terms of an abstract idea germinates. Tabulation of the data leads to Rules generation that in turn assists the Designing of the software system to implement the solution. Once the rules have been generated and the IT expert has prepared the databases to capture all rules, he/she can complete the coding and unit testing. The IT expert is now ready to do sample testing for the known data

The **fourth D** stands for **Development**: The design has to be pilot tested in a small area or an SBU before implementation for the organization as a whole. Here the IT expert can convert the *abstract idea* into *detailed reality* and based on the results of the pilot study, suitable amendments can be made in the program.. This stage basically gives the system for evaluation, incorporates changes as suggested by feedback and the final release of the ERP solution for implementation.

The **fifth D** stands for **Delivery** (or deployment): The software after alterations in the earlier stage is now ready for use. Stakeholders will be in little doubt about what the software can deliver and what they should reasonably expect from it. This will help to make a scientific and objective evaluation of the ERP package post implementation.

The sixth or **Hidden D** stands for **Data and Documentation** that is equally valid and important for all the above five Ds. Data Collection is important since an inaccurate data will generate only an inaccurate decision. And, Documentation is important so that data is preserved for future reference. Steps that will be involved in the extended study of this author are: (a) Preparation of questionnaire (b) Validating the questionnaire (either through Cronbach Alpha or Focused Interviews or both). (c) Distributing of the questionnaire to as many (relevant) respondents as possible and ensuring that at least 45% of the responses are received and are valid. (d) Tabulating the responses so as to enable ease of analysis. (e) Summarize the responses in a meaningful and understandable manner. Evaluating the outcome of ERP or the performance evaluation of the expert system is impossible without accurate and relevant data and documentation. Hence this is something that cannot be taken lightly.

To enable the argument to be developed further, this paper now posits a systems diagram to explain the expert system for decision making using through implementation of an ERP package. This diagram highlights three aspects needed for successful ERP implementation, which this author found in his pilot study viz. (i) Data Volume of the organization, (ii) Business and Operational complexity and (iii) Reporting complexity.

These three aspects aid in taking decisions about implementing ERP. For instance, large data volumes are unmanageable without an expert system. Business and operational complexity increases with the growth of the organization, which may require operating from multiple locations and having several SBUs. Small packages operating from stand-alone computers give quick output but their scope and geographical domain is limited. However, for ERP packages data complexity is huge leading to a reporting complexity and generation of reports is that much more complicated.

Generalized ERP Implementation Decision Process

5. CONCLUSION: Most of the organizations across the world have realized that in a rapidly changing environment, it is impossible to create and maintain a custom designed software package which will cater to all their requirements and also be completely up-to-date. ERP once implemented would ideally offer an integrated software solution to all the functions of the organization. ERP applications are notoriously complex and usually require extensive customization, recognizing these gains in any enterprise will require significant investments in time and money. The question arose: was the management prepared to make these investments? This paper was based on a pilot study covering ten organizations in Western India and brought to the fore certain observations about ERP implementation in the post WTO era. The author's used the 5-D Methodology to put forth his argument. This study highlighted three aspects that are needed for successful ERP implementation, namely data volume of the organization, business and operational complexity and reporting complexity. The study emphasized the importance of proper diagnosis (need analysis) and evaluation (post implementation) which, unfortunately many organizations take not so seriously. The result is that objective analysis does not take place and an otherwise powerful

package gets a poor name in the marketplace. The ethics of management as well as the consultant must be unimpeachable and the purpose of ERP implementation had to be *value based* as well as *value driven*. Finally, the five aspects that this study held to be responsible for the success of ERP were (a) the proper selling of the idea to stakeholders, (b) complete involvement of a specialist team, (c) accountability of those who recommend ERP implementation, (d) commitment and support from top management (CEO) and (e) strategic HR support.

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